

TESKARI MATRITSANI HISOBLASH USULLARI VA UNGA MOS DASTUR

YARATISH

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Agar A kvadrat matritsaning determinanti noldan farqli bo`lsa, ya`ni $A \neq 0$ bo`lsa, matritsa xosmas matritsa deyiladi.

Agar bo`lsa, matritsa xos matritsa deyiladi.

Agar $A \cdot A^{-1} = I$ tenglik o`rinli bo`lsa, A^{-1} matritsa A xosmas matritsaning teskari matritsasi deyiladi. Bu yerda I matritsa A matritsa o`lchovi bilan bir xil o`lchovli birlik matritsadir.

Xosmas matritsa uchun yagona teskari matritsa mavjud va quyidagi formula bilan hisoblanadi:

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{\det A} \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{21} & \dots & A_{n1} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & \dots & A_{n2} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ A_{1n} & A_{2n} & \dots & A_{nn} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix} \text{ matritsa uchun teskari } A^{-1} \text{ matritsani klassik usulda topamiz.}$$

Dastlab A matritsaning determinantini topib chiqamiz.

Determinant quyidagi formula asosida hisoblanadi:

$$|A| = (a_{11} * a_{22} * a_{33} + a_{12} * a_{23} * a_{31} + a_{13} * a_{21} * a_{32}) - (a_{13} * a_{22} * a_{31} + a_{12} * a_{21} * a_{33} + a_{11} * a_{23} * a_{32})$$

Agar $\det A \neq 0$ bo`lsa, u holda algebraik to`ldiruvchilarni topishni boshlaymiz.

$$A_{11} = (-1)^{1+1} * \begin{vmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} = a_{22} * a_{33} - a_{23} * a_{32}$$

$$A_{12} = (-1)^{1+2} * \begin{vmatrix} a_{21} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} = -(a_{21} * a_{33} - a_{23} * a_{31})$$

$$A_{13} = (-1)^{1+3} * \begin{vmatrix} a_{21} & a_{22} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} \end{vmatrix} = a_{21} * a_{32} - a_{22} * a_{31}$$

$$A_{21} = (-1)^{2+1} * \begin{vmatrix} a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} = a_{12} * a_{33} - a_{13} * a_{32}$$

$$A_{22} = (-1)^{2+2} * \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{13} \\ a_{31} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} = a_{11} * a_{33} - a_{13} * a_{31}$$

$$A_{23} = (-1)^{2+3} * \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} \end{vmatrix} = a_{11} * a_{32} - a_{12} * a_{31}$$

$$A_{31} = (-1)^{3+1} * \begin{vmatrix} a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{22} & a_{23} \end{vmatrix} = a_{12} * a_{23} - a_{13} * a_{22}$$

$$A_{32} = (-1)^{3+2} * \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{23} \end{vmatrix} = a_{11} * a_{23} - a_{13} * a_{21}$$

$$A_{33} = (-1)^{3+3} * \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{22} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix} = a_{11} * a_{22} - a_{12} * a_{22}$$

Agar $\det A \neq 0$ bo'lsa, u holda teskari matritsa topishni boshqa usulini ko'rib chiqamiz.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

Minorlarni qulay hisoblash maqsadida matritsaning birinchi ikkita satri pastga ko'chirib yoziladi va boshqa B matritsaga ko'chiriladi:

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \\ a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \end{pmatrix}$$

So'ng birinchi ikkita ustun o'ng tomonga qo'shiladi:

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{21} & a_{22} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} & a_{31} & a_{32} \\ a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

Keyingi bosqichda birinchi satr va birinchi ustun olib tashlanadi, natijada 2×2 determinantlarni hisoblash uchun qulay jadval hosil bo'ladi.

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{21} & a_{22} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} & a_{31} & a_{32} \\ a_{12} & a_{13} & a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{22} & a_{23} & a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

Mazkur bosqichda berilgan 3×3 o'lchamli matritsaning har bir elementi uchun mos minorlar aniqlanadi.

Ta'rifga ko'ra, M_{ij} minor — bu matritsaning i -satri va j -ustuni olib tashlangandan so'ng hosil bo'ladigan 2×2 o'lchamli yordamchi matritsaning determinantidir.

$$M_{12}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} \quad M_{23}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{23} & a_{21} \\ a_{33} & a_{31} \end{vmatrix} \quad M_{34}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{21} & a_{22} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$M_{12}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{32} & a_{33} \\ a_{12} & a_{13} \end{vmatrix} \quad M_{23}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{33} & a_{31} \\ a_{13} & a_{11} \end{vmatrix} \quad M_{34}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{31} & a_{32} \\ a_{11} & a_{12} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$M_{12}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{22} & a_{23} \end{vmatrix} \quad M_{23}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{13} & a_{11} \\ a_{23} & a_{21} \end{vmatrix} \quad M_{34}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} a_{23} & a_{21} \\ a_{33} & a_{31} \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} a_{21} & a_{22} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} \end{vmatrix} \\ \begin{vmatrix} a_{32} & a_{33} \\ a_{12} & a_{13} \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} a_{33} & a_{31} \\ a_{13} & a_{11} \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} a_{31} & a_{32} \\ a_{11} & a_{12} \end{vmatrix} \\ \begin{vmatrix} a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{22} & a_{23} \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} a_{13} & a_{11} \\ a_{23} & a_{21} \end{vmatrix} & \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix} \end{pmatrix}$$

Determinant nolga teng emasligi aniqlangach, berilgan matritsaning teskari matritsasini topish mumkin.

Chiziqli algebra nazariyasiga ko‘ra, n -tartibli kvadrat matritsaning teskari matritsasi quyidagi formula asosida aniqlanadi:

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} B^T$$

1-misol. 3×3 o‘lchamli matritsaning teskari matritsasini toping.

Berilgan matritsa:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 \\ 0 & 4 & 4 \end{pmatrix}$$

Mazkur masalada teskari matritsa avvalo minorlar usuli orqali topiladi, so‘ngra natija algebraik toldiruvchilar (kofaktorlar) usuli yordamida tekshiriladi.

1-bosqich. Matritsani kengaytirish

Minorlarni qulay hisoblash maqsadida matritsaning birinchi ikkita satri pastga ko‘chirib yoziladi:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 5 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 \\ 0 & 4 & 4 \\ 5 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

So‘ng birinchi ikkita ustun o‘ng tomonga qo‘shiladi:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 5 & 2 & 1 & 5 & 2 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 & 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 4 & 4 & 0 & 4 \\ 5 & 2 & 1 & 5 & 2 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 & 1 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Keyingi bosqichda birinchi satr va birinchi ustun olib tashlanadi, natijada 2×2 determinantlarni hisoblash uchun qulay jadval hosil bo‘ladi.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 3 & 2 & 1 & 3 \\ 4 & 4 & 0 & 4 \\ 2 & 1 & 5 & 2 \\ 3 & 2 & 1 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$$

2-bosqich. 2×2 determinantlarni hisoblash (Minorlarni aniqlash)

Mazkur bosqichda berilgan 3×3 o‘lchamli matritsaning har bir elementi uchun mos minorlar aniqlanadi.

Ta‘rifga ko‘ra, M_{ij} minor — bu matritsaning i -satri va j -ustuni olib tashlangandan so‘ng hosil bo‘ladigan 2×2 o‘lchamli yordamchi matritsaning determinantidir.

Umumiy ko‘rinishda:

$$M_{12}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} 3 & 2 \\ 4 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 12 - 8 = 4 \qquad M_{23}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 4 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = 0 - 4 = -4, \qquad M_{34}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 4 - 0$$

$$M_{12}^{23} = \begin{vmatrix} 4 & 4 \\ 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 4 - 8 = -4, \quad M_{23}^{23} = \begin{vmatrix} 4 & 0 \\ 1 & 5 \end{vmatrix} = 20 - 0 = 20,$$

$$M_{34}^{23} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 4 \\ 5 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 0 - 20 = -20$$

$$M_{12}^{34} = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 3 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 4 - 3 = 1,$$

$$M_{23}^{34} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 5 \\ 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 1 - 10 = -9,$$

$$M_{34}^{34} = \begin{vmatrix} 5 & 2 \\ 1 & 3 \end{vmatrix} = 15 - 2 = 13$$

Natijada quyidagi 3×3 minorlar matritsasi hosil bo‘ladi:

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} 4 & -4 & 4 \\ -4 & 20 & -20 \\ 1 & -9 & 13 \end{pmatrix}$$

3-bosqich. Determinantni hisoblash (Sarrus qoidasi asosida)

Berilgan 3×3 o‘lchamli matritsaning determinanti Sarrus qoidasi yordamida aniqlanadi. Ushbu qoida faqat 3×3 tartibli matritsalar uchun qo‘llaniladi va determinantni hisoblash jarayonini soddalashtiradi.

Berilgan matritsa:

$$|A| = \begin{vmatrix} 5 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 \\ 0 & 4 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = (60 + 4 + 0) - (0 + 40 + 8) = 16$$

Demak, $|A| = 16 \neq 0$ shuning uchun matritsa teskari matritsaga ega.

4-bosqich. Teskari matritsani aniqlash

Determinant nolga teng emasligi aniqlangach, berilgan matritsaning teskari matritsasini topish mumkin.

Chiziqli algebra nazariyasiga ko‘ra, n-tartibli kvadrat matritsaning teskari matritsasi quyidagi formula asosida aniqlanadi:

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} B^T$$

B matritsani transponirlaymiz:

$$B^T = \begin{pmatrix} 4 & -4 & 1 \\ -4 & 20 & -9 \\ 4 & -20 & 13 \end{pmatrix}$$

Transponirlangan B matritsa asosida teskari matritsani hisoblab chiqamiz.

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} B^T = \frac{1}{16} \begin{pmatrix} 24 & -4 & 1 \\ -4 & 20 & -9 \\ 4 & -20 & 13 \end{pmatrix}$$

Algebraik toldiruvchilar usuli orqali tekshirish

Endi olingan natijani kofaktorlar usuli bilan tekshiramiz.

Teskari matritsaning umumiy formulasi:

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{21} & A_{31} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{32} \\ A_{13} & A_{23} & A_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

Bu yerda:

$$A_{ij} = (-1)^{i+j} * M_{ij}$$

$\overline{M_{ij}}$ - mos minor to'ldiruvchisi.

Shu formulaga qo'yib hisoblab ko'ramiz:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 \\ 0 & 4 & 4 \end{pmatrix}, |A| = 16$$

$$A_{11} = 12 - 8 = 4$$

$$A_{21} = -(8 - 4) = -4$$

$$A_{31} = 4 - 3 = 1$$

$$A_{12} = -(4 - 0) = -4$$

$$A_{22} = 20 - 0 = 20$$

$$A_{32} = -(10 - 1) = -9$$

$$A_{13} = 4 - 0 = 4$$

$$A_{23} = -(20 - 0) = -20$$

$$A_{33} = 15 - 2 = 13$$

Qiymatlarni qo'yamiz:

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{16} \begin{pmatrix} 24 & -4 & 1 \\ -4 & 20 & -9 \\ 4 & -20 & 13 \end{pmatrix}$$

Natijalar o'zaro mos kelgani sababli hisoblash to'g'ri bajarilganligi tasdiqlandi.

Yuqoridagi misol va uning dasturiy yechimi bayon etilgach, algoritmnning qo'llanishi shu turdagi yana bir 3x3 matritsa misoli asosida davom ettiriladi va hisoblash jarayoni avvalgi tartibda amalga oshiriladi.

2-misol: A (3x3) matritsani teskari matritsasini toping.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 5 \end{pmatrix}$$

Avvalo matritsaning dastlabki ikki satri nusxalanib, jadvalning quyi qismiga ko'chiriladi.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 5 \\ 2 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Keyingi bosqichda dastlabki ikki ustun qiymatlari matritsaning yon tomoniga takroran kiritiladi.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 & 3 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 & 5 & 4 & 1 \\ 2 & 1 & 3 & 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

So'ng hisoblash jarayonini davom ettirish maqsadida birinchi ustun va birinchi satr jadvaldan chiqarib tashlanadi.

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 2 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 5 & 4 & 1 \\ 1 & 3 & 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Ta’rifga ko’ra, M_{ij} minor — bu matritsaning i -satri va j -ustuni olib tashlangandan so’ng hosil bo’ladigan 2×2 o’lchamli yordamchi matritsaning determinantidir.

Umumiy ko’rinishda:

$$M_{12}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ 1 & 5 \end{vmatrix} = 0 - 2 = -2, \quad M_{23}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 5 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 8 - 5 = 3, \quad M_{34}^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 4 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 1 - 0 = 1$$

$$M_{12}^{23} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 5 \\ 1 & 3 \end{vmatrix} = 3 - 5 = -2, \quad M_{23}^{23} = \begin{vmatrix} 5 & 4 \\ 3 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 10 - 12 = -2,$$

$$M_{34}^{23} = \begin{vmatrix} 4 & 1 \\ 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 4 - 2 = 4$$

$$M_{12}^{34} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 3 \\ 0 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 2 - 0 = 2,$$

$$M_{23}^{34} = \begin{vmatrix} 3 & 2 \\ 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 3 - 4 = -1,$$

$$M_{34}^{34} = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{vmatrix} = 0 - 1 = -1$$

Natijada quyidagi 3×3 minorlar matritsasi hosil bo’ladi:

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 3 & 1 \\ -2 & -2 & 4 \\ 2 & -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

B matritsa transponirlanib, uning B^T ko’rinishi hosil qilinadi.

$$B^T = \begin{pmatrix} -2 & -2 & 2 \\ 3 & -2 & -1 \\ 1 & 4 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Determinantni hisoblash (Sarrus qoidasi asosida)

Berilgan 3×3 o’lchamli matritsaning determinanti Sarrus qoidasi yordamida aniqlanadi. Ushbu qoida faqat 3×3 tartibli matritsalar uchun qo’llaniladi va determinantni hisoblash jarayonini soddalashtiradi.

Teskari matritsa topish formulasi:

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} B^T$$

Determinant quyidagi formula asosida hisoblanadi:

$$|A| = (a_{11} * a_{22} * a_{33} + a_{12} * a_{23} * a_{31} + a_{13} * a_{21} * a_{32}) - \\ - (a_{13} * a_{22} * a_{31} + a_{12} * a_{21} * a_{33} + a_{11} * a_{23} * a_{32})$$

Berilgan matritsa:

$$|A| = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 5 \end{vmatrix} = (0 + 8 + 3) - (0 + 4 + 5) = 2$$

Hisoblashlar yuqorida keltirilgan formula qo’llanilgan holda bajariladi.

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} B^T = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} -2 & -2 & 2 \\ 3 & -2 & -1 \\ 1 & 4 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Bu usulni tekshirish maqsadida Teskari matritsa topishning algebraik to'ldiruvchilar yordamida hisoblash usulini ko'ramiz:

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{|A|} \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{21} & A_{31} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{32} \\ A_{13} & A_{23} & A_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

Berilgan matritsa hamda determinantning qiymati:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 \\ 4 & 1 & 5 \end{pmatrix}, |A| = 2$$

Algebraik to'ldiruvchilar formulasi asosida matritsa elementlari hisoblanib, natijalar aniqlanadi.

$$A_{11} = 0 - 2 = -2 \quad A_{21} = -(5 - 3) = -2 \quad A_{31} = 2 - 0 = 2$$

$$A_{12} = -(5 - 8) = 3 \quad A_{22} = 10 - 12 = -2 \quad A_{32} = -(4 - 3) = -1$$

$$A_{13} = 1 - 0 = 1 \quad A_{23} = -(2 - 4) = 2 \quad A_{33} = 0 - 1 = -1$$

Topilgan qiymatlarni matritsaga kiritib, yakuniy ko'rinishni hosil qilamiz.

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} -2 & -2 & 2 \\ 3 & -2 & -1 \\ 1 & 4 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Demak, ikkala usul natijalari o'zaro mos ekanligi ko'rinadi.

Endi algoritmnini umumlashtirish maqsadida ixtiyoriy 3x3 o'lchamli matritsalar uchun ishlaydigan dastur kodini yozib chiqamiz.

```
def print_matrix(M, title=""):

    if title:

        print(title)

    for row in M:

        print(" ".join(f"{x:8.4f}" for x in row))

    print()

def determinant(A):

    n = len(A)

    if n == 1:

        return A[0][0]

    if n == 2:

        return A[0][0] * A[1][1] - A[0][1] * A[1][0]
```

```

det = 0

for j in range(n):
    minor = [row[:j] + row[j+1:] for row in A[1:]]
    det += ((-1) ** j) * A[0][j] * determinant(minor)

return det

```

```

def cofactor_matrix(A):
    n = len(A)
    C = [[0] * n for _ in range(n)]

    for i in range(n):
        for j in range(n):
            minor = [
                row[:j] + row[j+1:]
                for k, row in enumerate(A) if k != i
            ]
            C[i][j] = ((-1) ** (i + j)) * determinant(minor)

    return C

```

```

def transpose(A):
    return [list(row) for row in zip(*A)]

```

```

def inverse_matrix(A):
    detA = determinant(A)

    if detA == 0:

```

```
raise ValueError("Determinant 0 ga teng – teskari matritsa yo`q")

C = cofactor_matrix(A)
adjA = transpose(C)

n = len(A)
invA = [[adjA[i][j] / detA for j in range(n)] for i in range(n)]

return detA, invA

# Matritsa elementlarini input orqali olish (3x3)
A = []
print("3x3 matritsa elementlarini kiriting:")

for i in range(3):
    row = []
    for j in range(3):
        x = float(input(f"A[{i+1}][{j+1}] = "))
        row.append(x)
    A.append(row)

print_matrix(A, "A matritsa:")

detA, A_inv = inverse_matrix(A)

print(f"|A| = {detA}\n")
print_matrix(A_inv, "Teskari matritsa:")
```

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